

A Cross-Sectional Study to Determine Correlation Between Chronological Age and Radiological Stages of Development of Left Lower Third Molar Tooth in Age Group Between 15 to 22 Years by Using Modified Demirjian Method at SMS Medical College, Jaipur

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Dental age estimation using third molar development is widely employed in forensic practice, particularly during late adolescence when most permanent teeth have completed development. The Modified Demirjian Method (Acharya's), has been proposed for age estimation in Indian populations; however, its applicability in different regional populations requires validation. **Methodology:** A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 native residents of Jaipur aged 15–22 years who underwent orthopantomographic examination. Developmental stages of the left mandibular dentition (FDI 31–38) were assessed using the Modified Demirjian Method. Maturity scores were calculated and converted into dental age using sex-specific Acharya regression equations. Estimated dental age was compared with documented chronological age using appropriate statistical tests. **Result:** Third molar development demonstrated a progressive increase with advancing age. Stage 3&4 was observed exclusively in the 15–16 years age group, whereas Stage 8&9 predominated in individuals aged 21–22 years. Comparison of chronological age and estimated age revealed statistically significant differences in all age groups and both sexes ($p < 0.001$). The Acharya method consistently underestimated chronological age. Mean estimated ages for males and females were 12.38 ± 0.88 and 12.58 ± 0.92 years in the 15–16 years age group, and 18.87 ± 0.30 and 18.77 ± 0.30 years, respectively, in the 21–22 years age group. **Conclusion:** Third molar maturation showed a significant association with chronological age and remains a useful adjunct for forensic age estimation. However, Acharya's modified Demirjian method underestimated age in the Jaipur population, indicating the need for region-specific regression models and a multidisciplinary approach for medicolegal age assessment.

Keywords: Age estimation, Third molar, Demirjian method, Acharya formula, Orthopantomogram, Forensic odontology.

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INTRODUCTION:

Age estimation is a fundamental component of forensic identification and has significant applications in civil and criminal justice, immigration, sports eligibility, and age-related legal disputes. Accurate determination of age is particularly important in cases involving unidentified individuals, juveniles, unaccompanied minors, and asylum seekers. Among biological indicators, teeth are considered highly reliable because of their predictable developmental pattern and resistance to postmortem changes.^{1,2} Dental age estimation through radiographic assessment of tooth development is a widely accepted non-invasive method. While the development of most permanent teeth is completed by approximately 14 years of age, third molars continue to mature into late adolescence and early adulthood, making them valuable indicators for age estimation around the legally significant thresholds of 16 and 18 years.³ The staging system proposed by Demirjian et al. and its modified versions are among the most commonly used methods for evaluating third molar development and estimating age.⁴ However, dental maturation is influenced by genetic, environmental, nutritional, and socioeconomic factors, necessitating population-specific validation of age estimation methods.⁵ Most available standards have been developed using Western populations, and limited data exist for the population of Rajasthan. Jaipur district, characterized by its semi-arid climate, mixed urban-rural population, and distinct environmental conditions, provides a suitable setting for developing localized standards. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the applicability of the Modified Demirjian Method using mandibular third molars for age estimation in the Jaipur population and to assess its utility in determining the medicolegally important age thresholds of 16 and 18 years.

METHODOLOGY:

Aim: To evaluate the correlation between radiological stages of mandibular third molar development and chronological age using the Modified Demirjian Method among individuals aged 15–22 years from the Jaipur region, Rajasthan.

Objectives:

Primary Objectives

1. To assess the developmental stage of the left mandibular dentition (FDI teeth 31–38) using orthopantomograms (OPGs).
2. To calculate dental maturity scores according to the Modified Demirjian Method.
3. To estimate dental age using sex-specific regression equations.

4. To evaluate the applicability and accuracy of the Modified Demirjian Method for age estimation in the Jaipur population.

Secondary Objective

1. To determine the mean chronological age corresponding to each stage of mandibular third molar development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A hospital-based cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Departments of Forensic Medicine, Dentistry and Radiodiagnosis, SMS Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India, from October 2024 to March 2026.

Study Population The study included native residents of Jaipur region aged 15–22 years who underwent orthopantomographic examination for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes and provided written informed consent.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Individual/Patients who gave written informed consent.
2. Individual/Patients who have indication of OPG.
3. Individual/Patients between age group 15 years to 22 years of both sex (Age of medicolegal importance).
4. Radiographs of patient with full complement of teeth in the left mandibular quadrant.
5. Individual should be native of Jaipur region.
6. Individual Should Confirm their age by Original Documents Physically/Digitally.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Major ailments in the past affecting maxilla and mandible affecting growth and development in general and particular teeth.
2. History of injury leading to fracture, surgery of left mandibular region.
3. Patients who are clinically symptomatic and are diagnosed case of ricket, hypocalcaemia or other diseases which have impact on growth of tooth.
4. Patients who have symptoms or signs of fluorosis.
5. Congenital or acquired deformity of Face, skull, tooth.
6. Subjects with any kind of Procedure done in left side of teeth.

Total 100 participants were taken. Orthopantomograms were evaluated for the developmental stages of the left mandibular teeth (31–38) according to the Modified Demirjian Method. Each tooth was assigned a

developmental stage (0–9) and corresponding maturity score. The individual tooth scores were summed to obtain the total maturity score (S).

Statistical Analysis:

Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

Descriptive statistics were expressed as mean ± standard deviation and percentages.

Comparison between chronological age and estimated dental age was performed using paired t-test.

A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Dental age was estimated using the Indian-specific regression equations proposed by Acharya:

For males: Age = 27.4351 – (0.0097 × S²) + (0.000089 × S³)

For females: Age = 23.7288 – (0.0088 × S²) + (0.000085 × S³)

The estimated dental age was subsequently compared with the documented chronological age.

Table 1. Description of Developmental Stages (0–9) Used in the Modified Demirjian Method

Stage	Description
0	Absence of crypt or no radiopaque evidence of calcification.
1	Appearance of bony crypt; beginning of tooth development.
2	Initial calcification points appear at crypt tip; no fusion.
3	Fusion of calcified points; occlusal outline becomes visible.
4	Crown formation reaches approximately one-third to half of crown height.
5	Crown formation almost complete; dentino-enamel junction more distinct.
6	Crown formation complete up to cemento-enamel junction (CEJ); root formation begins.
7	Root length less than crown height; walls of root canal divergent.
8	Root length approximately equal to crown height; apical opening still present.
9	Complete root formation with apical closure (closed apex).

Figure 1. Ten Stages (0–9) of Tooth Development According to the Modified Demirjian Method

Representative radiographic and schematic illustrations showing the ten stages (0–9) of tooth development for molars, premolars, canines, and incisors. Stage 0 represents the absence of calcification, while Stage 9 indicates complete root formation with apical closure. These stages were used to assess dental maturity and estimate dental age in the present study. **Source:** Modified from Chaillet N, Demirjian A. (2004).

Table 2. Maturity Scores for Males Assigned to Developmental Stages (0–9) According to the Modified Demirjian Method

Stage	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38
0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.70	6.20
1	-	-	-	-	1.7	-	3.00	7.60
2	-	-	-	1.90	2.25	-	3.40	8.50
3	-	-	1.70	1.96	3.40	-	4.75	8.65
4	-	-	2.65	3.52	3.40	-	4.90	9.90
5	2.30	2.55	4.35	5.19	5.60	2.15	6.70	11.15
6	4.35	4.70	6.15	6.47	6.95	3.75	7.90	12.25
7	5.15	5.75	7.60	8.18	8.70	4.95	9.10	13.65
8	6.55	6.95	9.50	9.84	10.65	7.00	11.15	14.05
9	10.70	10.80	12.55	14.25	13.10	11.20	13.65	15.30

Table 3. Maturity Scores for Females Assigned to Developmental Stages (0–9) According to the Modified Demirjian Method

Stage	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38
0								6.40
1							2.55	7.75
2					2.45			8.90
3				2.55	3.45		2.65	9.30
4			2.55	3.55	3.85		4.10	10.20
5	2.60	2.65	3.15	5.10	5.75	2.60	6.50	11.05
6	3.10	4.55	5.40	6.30	6.80	3.25	8.00	12.65
7	5.00	5.40	7.20	8.10	8.70	4.25	9.15	13.75
8	6.65	7.00	9.20	9.80	10.80	6.90	11.00	14.45
9	10.60	10.90	12.00	12.30	12.80	10.95	13.85	16.65

RESULTS:

A total of 100 subjects aged 15–22 years were included in the study, comprising 50 males and 50 females. The largest proportion of participants belonged to the 15–16 years age group (26%), followed by the 17–18 years and 19–20 years age groups (25% each), while the 21–22 years age group accounted for 24% of the study population.

Most participants were Hindus (81%), students (52%), and followed a vegetarian diet (74%). Regarding

nutritional status, 42% of subjects were overweight (BMI 25–29.9 kg/m²), 34% had normal BMI, while 12% each were underweight and obese class I. Average dental hygiene was observed in 57% of participants, followed by good hygiene in 34% and poor hygiene in 9%. Good dental hygiene was more frequent among higher-income groups, whereas poor dental hygiene was predominantly observed among lower-income families.

Table 4: Distribution of Third Molar (M3) Developmental Stages According to Age Group

3 RD Molar Tooth Stage	No. of Cases of Age Group (Yrs)								Total
	15-16		17-18		19-20		21-22		
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	
3	7	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	00
5	6	7	4	9	0	0	0	0	26
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	00
7	0	0	8	4	6	7	0	0	25
8	0	0	0	0	6	6	12	12	36
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	00
Total	13	13	13	12	12	13	12	12	100

Third molar development showed a progressive increase with advancing age. Stage 3 was observed exclusively in the 15–16 years age group (13%), while Stage 5 was predominant among subjects aged 15–18 years (26%). Stage 7 was mainly observed in the 17–20 years age groups (25%), whereas Stage 8 was the most common stage overall (36%) and was present in all subjects aged 21–22 years. No participants exhibited Stages 4, 6, or 9.

Table 5: Comparison of Chronological Age and Age Estimated by Acharya Method According to Age Group and Sex

Age Group (Years)	Sex	n	Chronological Age (Mean ± SD)	Acharya Estimated Age (Mean ± SD)
15–16	Male	13	15.86 ± 0.64	12.38 ± 0.88
15–16	Female	13	16.05 ± 0.51	12.58 ± 0.92
17–18	Male	13	17.44 ± 0.30	13.31 ± 0.06
17–18	Female	12	18.50 ± 0.33	15.51 ± 0.14
19–20	Male	12	19.30 ± 0.26	15.48 ± 0.14
19–20	Female	13	20.40 ± 0.36	18.55 ± 1.01
21–22	Male	12	21.40 ± 0.34	18.87 ± 0.30
21–22	Female	12	21.68 ± 0.19	18.77 ± 0.30

The mean chronological age and estimated age by the Acharya method demonstrated consistent differences across all age groups. In the 15–16 years age group, the mean estimated age was 12.38 ± 0.88 years in males and 12.58 ± 0.92 years in females compared with chronological ages of 15.86 ± 0.64 and 16.05 ± 0.51 years, respectively. Similarly, in the 17–18 years age group, estimated ages were 13.31 ± 0.06 years in males and 15.51 ± 0.14 years in females, compared with chronological ages of 17.44 ± 0.30 and 18.50 ± 0.33 years.

Among participants aged 19–20 years, the mean estimated age was 15.48 ± 0.14 years in males and 18.55 ± 1.01 years in females, whereas the corresponding chronological ages were 19.30 ± 0.26 and 20.40 ± 0.36 years. In the 21–22 years age group, estimated ages were 18.87 ± 0.30 years in males and 18.77 ± 0.30 years in females compared with chronological ages of 21.40 ± 0.34 and 21.68 ± 0.19 years, respectively. Paired t-test analysis demonstrated statistically significant differences between chronological age and age estimated by the Acharya method in all age groups for both males and females ($p < 0.001$). The findings indicate that the Acharya method consistently underestimated chronological age across the entire study population, with the magnitude of underestimation increasing with advancing age.

DISCUSSION:

Dental age estimation is an important tool in forensic medicine, particularly during late adolescence and early adulthood when third molars continue their development after completion of most permanent teeth. Third molar maturation has been widely used for age estimation because dental calcification is considered a reliable indicator of biological maturity and is less influenced by environmental factors than skeletal development.^{1–3}

In the present study, third molar developmental stages showed a progressive increase with chronological age. Subjects aged 15–16 years predominantly exhibited Stages 3 and 5, while Stages 5 and 7 were common in the 17–18 years age group. Most participants aged 19–20 years demonstrated Stages 7 and 8, whereas all subjects aged 21–22 years showed Stage 8. These findings are consistent with those reported by Demirjian et al.⁴, Naik et al.¹⁰, and Jung et al.¹¹, who observed a strong association between advancing age and third molar maturation.

Comparison of chronological age with age estimated using Acharya's modified Demirjian formula revealed statistically significant differences in all age groups and both sexes ($p < 0.001$). The method consistently underestimated chronological age, with the degree of underestimation increasing in older age groups. Similar findings were reported by Mohanty et al.¹⁶ and Chhapparwal et al.¹⁹, who emphasized the need for population-specific validation of age estimation formulas. In contrast, Jaiswal et al.²² and Kumar and Gopal⁹ reported better agreement between estimated and chronological age in other Indian populations.

Sex-wise analysis showed only minor differences between males and females, although females demonstrated slightly closer agreement with chronological age in older age groups. Comparable observations have been reported by Indra Priyadharshini et al.¹² and Sheefaa MI et al.²⁰.

The findings of the present study suggest that third molar development remains a useful indicator of chronological age; however, Acharya's regression formula showed limited accuracy in the Jaipur population due to consistent age underestimation. These results support the need for development of region-specific regression equations to improve the accuracy and forensic applicability of dental age estimation in Rajasthan.

LIMITATIONS:

1. The study was conducted at a single tertiary care center.
2. The sample size was relatively small.
3. Only native residents of Jaipur region were included.
4. Environmental and genetic factors influencing tooth development were not evaluated.
5. Results may not be generalizable to other populations.

CONCLUSION:

The present study demonstrated a progressive relationship between third molar development and chronological age, supporting the utility of dental maturation as an adjunctive tool for forensic age estimation. However, Acharya's modified Demirjian method significantly underestimated chronological age in all age groups and both sexes, indicating limited accuracy in the Jaipur population.

These findings suggest that third molar assessment should not be used as a standalone method for medicolegal age determination. Greater accuracy may be achieved by combining dental age estimation with physical examination and skeletal age assessment. Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach integrating dental, physical, and radiological parameters is recommended for forensic age evaluation.

Further multicentric studies with larger sample sizes are required to develop and validate population-specific regression models for improving the accuracy and reliability of age estimation in the Indian population.

Data Availability Statement:

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Informed Consent:

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants included in the study.

Author Contributions:

Dr. Mahesh Soni, Data collection, manuscript preparation. Dr. Rajesh Kumar Verma, Conceptualization, supervision, manuscript review. Dr. Ram Lakhani Meena, Data acquisition and analysis. Dr. N L Disania,

Methodology and validation. Dr. Sumanta Dutta, Critical review and final approval.

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee and Institutional Research Review Board of SMS Medical College, Jaipur (Ref. No. 1290/MC/EC/2024).

Conflict of Interest: Nil

Funding Source: Nil

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REFERENCES:

1. Schmeling A, Geserick G, Reisinger W, Olze A. Age estimation. *Forensic Sci Int.* 2007;165(2-3):178-81.
2. Ritz-Timme S, Cattaneo C, Collins MJ, Waite ER, Schütz HW, Kaatsch HJ, et al. Age estimation: the state of the art in relation to forensic practice. *Int J Legal Med.* 2000;113(3):129-36.
3. Lewis JM, Senn DR. Dental age estimation utilizing third molar development: a review of principles, methods and population studies. *Forensic Sci Int.* 2010;201(1-3):79-83.
4. Demirjian A, Goldstein H, Tanner JM. A new system of dental age assessment. *Hum Biol.* 1973;45(2):211-27.
5. Kumar VJ, Gopal KS. Reliability of age estimation using Demirjian's 8 teeth method and India-specific formula. *J Forensic Dent Sci.* 2011;3(1):19-27.
6. Naik SB, Patil SN, Kamble SD, Mowade T, Motghare P. Reliability of third molar development for age estimation by radiographic examination using Demirjian's method. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2014;8(9):ZC25-ZC28.
7. Jung HJ, Lee SS, Choi JH, Yoon CL. Radiographic evaluation of 3rd molar development for age estimation in adolescents and young adults. *Forensic Sci Int.* 2014.
8. Indra Priyadharshini, Jeevan MB, Subramanian EMG. Applicability of Demirjian's method for age estimation in Indian population. *J Forensic Dent Sci.* 2015.
9. Bijjaragi SC, et al. Dental age estimation by Demirjian's method among Indian subjects. *J Forensic Dent Sci.* 2015.
10. Priyanka M, et al. Evaluation of dental maturity and age estimation in Indian population. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2018.
11. Mohanty R, et al. Evaluation of Acharya's formula for dental age estimation in eastern Indian population. 2019.
12. Chhapparwal Y, et al. Applicability of Demirjian-based age estimation methods in South Indian population. 2021.
13. Sheefaa MI, et al. Assessment of Demirjian method for age estimation among young adults. 2023.
14. Sindi A, et al. Population variations in dental age estimation using third molar development. 2023.
15. Jaiswal A, et al. Evaluation of modified Demirjian method for age estimation in North Indian population. 2024.